

Studies in Furan Derivatives. Part I. Synthesis of Naphtho- and 1,6-Dimethylnaphtho-(2,1-b,6,5-b')difurans

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The title compounds have been synthesised from 1,5-diformyl- and 1, 5-diacetyl-2, 6-dihydroxynaphthalene, respectively, by condensation with ethyl bromoacetate and subsequent hydrolysis, cyclisation, and decarboxylation of the 1,5-diformyl- and 1,5-diacetyl-2, 6-bis-(ethoxycarbonylmethoxy) naphthalene formed. An improved method for the synthesis of 1, 5-diformyl-2, 6-dihydroxynaphthalene is also described.

The present work deals with the synthesis of naphtho- and 1,6-dimethylnaphtho-(2;1-b, 6,5-b')difurans which have not been synthesised so far. For the synthesis of the former, 1,5-diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene was required as an intermediate which could be obtained only in low yields by methods reported earlier¹⁻³. It has now been prepared in 55% yield by the Sommelet reaction on the Mannich base, 2, 6-dihydroxy-1, 5-bis-(dimethylaminomethyl)naphthalene, obtained in the course of a separate study³.

1,5-Diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the di-ester obtained was hydrolysed to the corresponding dicarboxylic acid with ethanolic KOH. On heating with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, it furnished the naphthodifuran(I,a) on simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation.

- (a): R = R' = H.
(b): R = R' = Me.

For the synthesis of 1, 6-dimethylnaphtho-(2, 1-b, 6,5-b') difuran (I,b), 1,5-diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene⁴ was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the ester obtained was hydrolysed. The dicarboxylic acid on heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride and on simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation furnished the required difuran derivative.

1. Farbenfabriken Bayer A. G., B. P. 704,863/1958; *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 320.
2. Dewar and Talati, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 1592.
3. Unpublished work.
4. Fieser and Lothrop, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1459.

*EXPERIMENTAL

2,6-Dihydroxynaphthalene was prepared in a better yield (50%) by slightly modifying the earlier method⁵. The alkali fusion of sodium salt of 2-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid was carried out in a Muffle furnace at 400-25° for 1½ hr.

2,6-Dihydroxy-1,5-bis-(dimethylaminomethyl)naphthalene. — To paraformaldehyde (0.9 g.), dissolved in warm ethanol (10 ml), was added dimethylamine (3 ml, 37% aq. soln.) with external cooling. 2,6-Dihydroxynaphthalene (1.8 g.) in ethanol was then added. The product, which separated immediately, was crystallised from benzene in white plates (1.3 g.), m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 70.22; H, 7.95; N, 0.84. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires C, 70.06; H, 8.03; N, 10.22%).

1,5-Diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene. — The preceding compound (2 g.) was refluxed gently with hexamethylenetetramine (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) till the colour of the reaction mixture turned orange-red (approx. 1/2 hr.). It was then poured on water and the product separating was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 270°, yield 0.8 g. Mixed m.p. with a sample prepared by the known method was not depressed.

1,5-Diformyl-2,6-bis-(ethoxycarbonylmethoxy)naphthalene. — 1,5-Diformyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (2 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) in dry acetone for 2 hr. on a water bath. The reaction mixture was then poured on water and the ester separating was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 191°. (Found: C, 62.20; H, 5.39. $C_{20}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 61.86; H, 5.15%).

1,5-Diformyl-2,6-bis-(carboxymethoxy)naphthalene. — The above ester (1.5 g.) was heated on a water bath with 5% EtOH-KOH for 2 hr. The clear liquid on acidification afforded the dicarboxylic acid, crystallising from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 270°, yield 1 g. (Found after drying at 110° under vacuum: C, 57.76; H, 3.54. $C_{16}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 57.84; H, 3.62%).

Naphtho-(2,1-b,6,5-b')difuran. — The preceding acid (1 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride on a wire gauze for 2½ hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on water and kept overnight. The solid separating was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 175°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 80.86; H, 4.02. $C_{14}H_8O_4$ requires C, 80.76; H, 3.85%).

1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-bis-(ethoxycarbonylmethoxy)naphthalene. — 1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene (1.5 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (2 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in dry acetone on a water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on water and the product separating was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 155°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 63.70; H, 6.13. $C_{22}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 63.46; H, 5.77%).

1,5-Diacetyl-2,6-bis-(carboxymethoxy)naphthalene. — The above ester (1 g.) was heated on a water bath with 10% EtOH-NaOH for 1½ hr. and the clear solution obtained was acidified. The solid obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in small white crys-

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

5. Willstätter and Parnas, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1406.

tals (0.6 g.), m.p. 290°. (Found after drying at 110° under vacuum: C, 59.66; H, 4.22. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 60.01; H, 4.44%).

1,0-Dimethylnaphtho-(2, 1-b, 6, 5-b')difuran.—The above acid (0.6 g.) was refluxed on a wire gauze with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on water and kept overnight. The product separating was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in shining white crystals (0.3 g.), m.p. 225°. (Found: C, 80.86; H, 5.25. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.00%).

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